

What makes readers love a fiction book: A statistical analysis on *Wild Wise Weird* using real-world data from Amazon readers' reviews

Minh-Hoang Nguyen ^{1*}, Ni Putu Wulan Purnama Sari ², Minh-Phuong Thi Duong ³,
Manh-Tung Ho ^{1,4}, Thi Mai Anh Tran ⁵, Dan Li ⁶, Phuong-Tri Nguyen ⁷, Hong-Hoa Thi
Nguyen ⁸, Viet-Phuong La ^{1,9}

¹ Centre for Interdisciplinary Social Research, Phenikaa University, Hanoi, Vietnam

² Faculty of Nursing, Widya Mandala Surabaya Catholic University, East Java, Indonesia

³ Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities, Ton Duc Thang University, Ho Chi Minh
City, Vietnam

⁴ Institute of Philosophy, Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences, Hanoi, Vietnam

⁵ College of Forest Resources and Environmental Science, Michigan Technological
University, Houghton, USA

⁶ Yan'an University, Yan'an, China

⁷ Securities Research and Training Center, State Security Commission, Ho Chi Minh,
Vietnam

⁸ Ho Chi Minh College of Economics and Technology, Ho Chi Minh, Vietnam

⁹ A.I. for Social Data Lab (AISDL), Vuong & Associates, Hanoi, Vietnam

* Correspondence: hoang.nguyenminh@phenikaa-uni.edu.vn

August 06, 2025

[Original working draft v4 / Un-peer-reviewed]

Abstract

For centuries, fiction—particularly fables—has seamlessly combined storytelling, moral lessons, and societal reflections to engage readers on both emotional and intellectual levels. Despite extensive research on the benefits of reading and the emotional responses it evokes, a critical gap remains in understanding what drives readers to form deep emotional connections with specific works. This study seeks to identify the characteristics of a book that foster such connections. Using the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework analytics, we analyzed a dataset of 129 Amazon reviews of *Wild Wise Weird*, a collection of 42 fables that intertwine traditional storytelling with contemporary sensibilities, offering life lessons, humor, and social commentary. Of these reviews, approximately 66% expressed love for the book. The findings reveal that readers who describe the book as unique, whimsical, quirky, or innovative are more likely to express emotional attachment to it. Similarly, readers who are drawn to the book’s illustrations and characters tend to form stronger emotional connections. The cultural richness and representativeness of the book also emerged as significant factors in fostering readers’ emotional attachment. The book successfully captures the depth, charm, and moral essence of Vietnamese culture to a global audience while conveying a minimal sense of humor in the Zhuangzian (莊子) tradition. Readers have expressed heartfelt gratitude after engaging with the book, underscoring its success in fostering meaningful emotional connections. Thus, insights from this analysis offer actionable recommendations for stakeholders in the literary ecosystem, from authors and publishers to marketers, to enhance readers’ emotional attachment and commitment to books.

Keywords: book loving; readers; satirical fable; innovative book; cultural richness; paintings; authors

Plain Language Summary

For centuries, stories—especially fables—have been a powerful way to share life lessons, spark emotions, and reflect on society. While many studies have shown that reading can be emotional and meaningful, we still do not fully understand what makes readers form a deep emotional bond with a particular book. This study set out to explore that question. We looked at 129 Amazon reviews of *Wild Wise Weird*, a collection of 42 fables that feature the quirky bird village with the Kingfisher, as the main character. The fables mix Zhuangzian (莊子) humor with fresh ideas, satires, and social messages about timeless

and timely issues of our time. What we found was clear: people who described the book as unique, whimsical, quirky, or innovative were more likely to say they loved it. Many also connected deeply with the book's characters and beautiful illustrations. Another important reason readers felt attached to the book was its cultural richness. The book shares Vietnamese culture in a heartfelt and meaningful way that resonates with readers from around the world. Many people even wrote messages of gratitude, saying the book made a lasting impact on them. Our study is one of the first to use quantitative data to explore the factors that contribute to people's love of fiction books. The results offer helpful insights for a wide range of people. Teachers can use these findings to choose books that connect better with students. Writers can learn how to craft stories that truly speak to their readers. Publishers can more easily spot books that will make a strong emotional impact.

"His love for all things beautiful aside, Kingfisher also wants to ensure his public image is well-received, and so he decides that he must work together with Owl to produce the perfect portrait."

In "The Most Beautiful Bird"; *Wild Wise Weird* (2024)

"A frog in a well cannot discuss the ocean, because he is limited by the size of his well. A summer insect cannot discuss ice, because it knows only its own season. A narrow-minded scholar cannot discuss the Tao, because he is constrained by his teachings."

In "Season of Autumn Floods"; *The Book of Chuang Tzu* (2006)

1. Introduction

Books play a vital role in human development, serving as instruments for education, cultural preservation, and personal growth (Crawford et al., 2024; Serenko et al., 2012). Within this landscape, fiction has emerged as a particularly influential genre, accounting for 53.42% of all printed book sales in the United States as of 2023 (Watson, 2024) and 78% of all-time bestsellers (Curcic, 2023). The popularity of fiction has prompted extensive research demonstrating its significance for readers' psychological and social development. Studies found that fiction reading positively correlates with enhanced

social support (Mar et al., 2009), improved interpersonal sensitivity (Fong et al., 2013), deeper thinking (Koopman & Hakemulder, 2015), promotes empathy and prosocial behavior (Bal & Veltkamp, 2013; Stansfield & Bunce, 2014), and supported better well-being (Mendrofa, 2020; Thumala Olave, 2018).

Among the various genres of fiction, fables occupy a unique and significant position. For centuries, fables have blended storytelling, moral lessons, and reflections on society in a way that captivates readers both emotionally and intellectually (Chauvin et al., 2019; Çubukçu, 2011; Kgopa & Mathe, 2022; Park, 2022; Smith, 2015; Soni, 2024). Using anthropomorphized animals as characters, fables stimulate imagination and provide a safe space for exploring complex themes, effectively instilling values and ethical behaviors in readers, particularly children (Abrar, 2016; Pelletier & Beatty, 2015; Soni, 2024). Fables also serve as powerful tools for examining broader societal issues and dynamics, such as power structures, justice, social hierarchies, and the human condition (Kgopa & Mathe, 2022). The adaptability of fables has enabled them to address contemporary concerns, with modern authors reinterpreting traditional narratives through feminist lenses to challenge gender norms and advocate for social justice (Mangsong, 2019). Educators have also successfully integrated fables into various disciplines, including science education, to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes (Lisnani, 2019). Given the enduring influence of fables on readers' development, understanding what drives readers to form deep emotional connections with these narratives is crucial for educators, authors, and publishers seeking to promote works that resonate with readers while advancing educational goals and preserving cultural knowledge.

Existing research has explored the emotional bond between readers and books, characterizing the love of books as a deep and emotional connection that provides enjoyment, entertainment, and emotional fulfillment (Konrad, 2023; Read et al., 2011; Rothbauer & Harrington, 2022; Thumala Olave, 2020; Waheed et al., 2015). This emotional attachment to books and narratives is often observed as a potential barrier to the adoption of e-book readers (Spence, 2020; Waheed et al., 2015). Book lovers are also characterized by their high frequency of reading, commitment to the practice (Merga & Roni, 2018; Southerton et al., 2012), and enthusiasm for sharing their experiences and recommending books to peers and communities (Ivey, 2014; Merga et al., 2017; Merga & Roni, 2018; Paredes & Aliagas, 2022).

Despite the growing body of research on the benefits of reading and readers' emotional responses, a critical gap exists in understanding the specific factors that drive readers to form deep emotional connections with particular works (Best, 2021; Cho et al., 2021; Luțan & Bădică, 2022; Reagan et al., 2016; Zhang & Liu, 2022). For example, while recent studies by Cho et al. (2021) and Luțan and Bădică (2022) have employed text mining to analyze emotional content in book reviews, these investigations remain primarily descriptive, failing to identify the underlying mechanisms that foster profound reader engagement. To the best of our knowledge, data-driven, quantitative analyses offering actionable insights into what makes readers love specific books are scarce.

To address this gap, our study aims to explore the characteristics of the book that contribute to readers' love for fiction books. By utilizing the Granular Interaction Thinking Theory and Bayesian Mindsponge Framework analytics, we analyzed a dataset of 129 book reviews on *Wild Wise Weird* of Professor Vuong Quan Hoang, a collection of 42 fables that blends traditional storytelling with modern sensibilities, weaving together life lessons, humor, and social commentary (Vuong, 2024). This book was chosen for several reasons. First and foremost, it is a book that we personally love, and we are interested in understanding what makes others love it as well. Second, it has received a widely positive rating (4.9/5.0 on Amazon and 4.9/5.0 on Goodreads) from readers across diverse socio-cultural contexts, suggesting its broad appeal. Third, the book's contents are relevant to contemporary issues, with themes that resonate with modern readers' concerns and values, such as freedom, justice, honesty, responsibility, peace, environmental sustainability, and the complex relationship between humans and nature.

By examining how a fiction book, particularly a fable, creates deep emotional and intellectual connections with readers across different backgrounds, this study provides a systematic understanding of what drives the reader's attachment. Given the limited quantitative research on what makes readers love fiction books, our data-driven approach represents one of the first comprehensive investigations into this relationship. The study findings are expected to deliver actionable insights for multiple stakeholders in the literary ecosystem. Educators can utilize the findings to select strategies that resonate with students. Authors can gain evidence-based guidance for crafting more engaging narratives that resonate deeply with readers. Publishers can better identify and market books with strong potential for reader connection, ultimately improving their ability to bring impactful works to market. Finally, this research contributes to the

growing understanding of the psychological and emotional dimensions of reader engagement in literature, ultimately enhancing the reading culture of the general public.

2. Method

2.1. Theoretical Foundation

The granular interaction thinking theory (GITT), an updated development of mindsponge theory, was used in the conceptual development of this study (Vuong & Nguyen, 2024a, 2024b). Mindsponge theory, the mind's information-processing theory, is a cognitive framework that explains how individuals process, filter, and internalize information, particularly within socio-cultural settings, as the theoretical foundation. It operates on key cognitive principles, including self-balancing, cost-benefit analysis, goal alignment, and energy conservation, all aimed at fostering personal growth and adaptation (Vuong, 2023). Recently, mindsponge theory has been upgraded into a granular interaction thinking theory (GITT) by integrating concepts of quantum physics and Shannon's information theory (Hertog, 2023; Rovelli, 2018; Shannon, 1948). The updated mindsponge theory, or GITT, views information as possible alternatives (Shannon, 1948).

From the perspective of GITT, the mind functions as a dynamic system that processes and filters information within its environmental and informational surroundings, collectively referred to as the infosphere. GITT uses the "sponge" metaphor to illustrate how people selectively absorb or reject cultural values based on their relevance to personal beliefs or the surrounding environment (Vuong & Nguyen, 2024a). This information-processing mechanism, the mindsponge mechanism, is the core of GITT. At the mind's core is the "mindset," a collection of core values that guide psychological processes and behaviors, including the evaluation of new information. Information aligning with these core values and perceived as beneficial is integrated, reinforcing cognitive processes in a self-sustaining cycle. Conversely, conflicting information is typically rejected.

GITT introduces an entropy-based notion of value, positing that values arise through the interactions between internal cognitive information and external inputs from the infosphere. These interactions reduce entropy—that is, uncertainty or unpredictability—in ways that promote human development. Applied to fiction, this perspective suggests that each instance of reader-text engagement incrementally resolves narrative

uncertainties (e.g., regarding plot, character, or thematic meaning), generating emotional and cognitive rewards that reinforce the reader's sense-making process.

The GITT perspective aligns closely with several well-established literary theories, particularly reader-response theory, affect theory, and narrative empathy. Reader-response theorists emphasize the active role of the reader in generating meaning through interaction with the text (Fish, 1995; Iser, 1972; Mart, 2019; Rosenblatt, 1978). According to Iser (1972), a literary work consists of two poles: the artistic, referring to the text created by the author, and the aesthetic, representing the realization accomplished by the reader. Meaning, then, emerges at the "convergence of text and reader," which "brings the literary work into existence". Similarly, Rosenblatt (1978) conceptualizes reading as a transactional process, asserting that the reader is "not seen as a separate entity, acting upon the environment, nor [is] the environment acting on the organism, but both parts acting as a total event" (p. 98). This view underscores the mutual influence between reader and text in constructing meaning.

While reader-response theory foregrounds meaning-making, affect theory draws attention to the role of emotion, bodily responses, and feeling in aesthetic and cultural experience. Massumi (1995) describes emotion as a subjective content, "the socio-linguistic fixing of the quality of an experience," that has been captured and contextualized by the mind, or "owned and recognized". Building on this, Ahmed (2004) characterizes emotions as relational practices that shape boundaries between self and other. In literary reading, this implies that emotions do not merely reside within the reader but serve as bridges that connect the reader to the fictional world and broader socio-cultural understandings. Narrative empathy emerges as one of the outcomes of affective engagement with fiction. Keen (2006) defines it as the vicarious, spontaneous sharing of affect that can be prompted by reading, viewing, hearing, or imagining narratives of another's situation and condition. This form of empathy encompasses both affective and cognitive dimensions: readers may experience emotions parallel to those of the characters (joy, fear, sorrow) while also engaging in perspective-taking and interpreting characters' mental states. Fiction provides a safe and immersive simulation in which readers can experience events "as if the reader experiences the events [personally]" (Bal & Veltkamp, 2013).

GITT offers a dynamic framework to synthesize and extend these theories. From the GITT perspective, reading is conceptualized as a continual interaction between the information

stored in the reader's mind and the narrative information encoded in the text. These interactions occur at a granular level, with each moment of engagement—whether decoding a plot development, interpreting a metaphor, or reflecting on a character's action—constituting an instance of cognitive-affective processing. Readers apply interpretive schemas and prior knowledge to make sense of textual elements, reducing narrative ambiguity or entropy in the process. Concurrently, narrative inputs generate affective micro-responses—curiosity, suspense, compassion—which loop back into the reader's information-processing, shaping subsequent meaning-making. These feedback mechanisms influence how informational pathways unfold during reading, guiding the reduction of uncertainty and the construction of value. Because GITT is oriented toward human-beneficial outcomes, the emotional rewards of reading—pleasure, catharsis, empathy, excitement—can be seen as emergent values co-produced through reader-text interaction.

Moreover, when readers empathize with characters from different backgrounds or worldviews, they are more likely to absorb new socio-cultural and emotional information. This process narrows the psychological distance between the reader and character, aligning affective states and facilitating cognitive-affective integration. Through this alignment, the complexities of unfamiliar lives and contexts—previously “disordered” from the reader's perspective—become more comprehensible and meaningful. The resulting shifts in perception may prompt readers to reevaluate existing beliefs and cultivate heightened emotional sensibilities, such as love.

There is currently no universal consensus on the definition of love. Love is a multi-faceted concept with diverse characteristics, and even scientific, philosophical, and folk traditions struggle to agree on a singular definition (Fehr & Russell, 1991; Reis & Aron, 2008; Thumala Olave, 2020, 2022). The natural language concept of love—encompassing maternal love, romantic love, affection, love of work, self-love, and more—possesses an internal structure with fuzzy boundaries (Fehr & Russell, 1991). For the purposes of this study, we adopt the definition proposed by Reis and Aron (2008), which conceptualizes love as a desire to establish, maintain, or deepen a close, connected, and enduring relationship with another person or entity. In other words, fiction book-loving can be interpreted as a phenomenon reflecting one's emotional attachment and commitment to the book (Thumala Olave, 2020).

GITT frames love as the output of an information-processing system. According to GITT, love is a subjective mental state expressed through emotional attachment and commitment toward an object, person, or entity. This subjectivity makes love elusive, as it is deeply shaped by individual socio-cultural backgrounds and experiences while also being dynamically influenced by interacting with newly absorbed information. As a result, readers' emotional attachment and commitment toward a book can be shaped by their preferences and experiences, as well as through reading the book. Through engaging with a compelling storyline, readers gain deeper insights into the characters' personalities and the situations they encounter, processing new information as they follow the narrative. Each granular piece of information interacts, connects, and integrates with existing information within the readers' minds, reducing the entropy and forming synthetic information, or perceived value, of the book's content. The greater the perceived values, the more likely the book's content is absorbed and internalized into the mind's mindset, forming stronger emotional connections with the book. This reasoning aligns with Nussbaum (2001)'s cognitive-evaluative theory of emotion, which posits that emotions are not simply physiological responses, but rather are intelligent responses to perceived value. In this view, experiencing an emotion like love involves making a judgment that someone or something is of significant importance to one's well-being and flourishing. For example, if details about characters' backgrounds, personalities, cultural values, humor, life experiences, and tense events are aligned with readers' core values and evoke pleasant feelings, foster attachment, and inspire positive emotions, they will support self-understanding, self-care, and ethical reflection in readers (Thumala Olave, 2022).

Based on this theoretical reasoning, we construct a model examining the book's characteristics that can foster the book-loving feeling or emotional connections to the book.

2.2. Model construction

2.2.1. Variable generation

In this study, Amazon book reviews of *Wild Wise Weird*, published online, served as the primary data source for statistical analysis (see Figure 1). *Wild Wise Weird* is a collection of 42 fables that blends traditional storytelling with modern sensibilities, interweaving life lessons, humor, and social commentary (Vuong, 2024). Rooted in Vietnamese culture,

the book offers a satirical lens on society, inviting readers to reflect on humanistic values such as justice, honesty, responsibility, freedom, and community. It also addresses pressing contemporary issues like peace, environmental sustainability, and the intricate relationship between humans and nature.

Figure 1. *Wild Wise Weird* on Amazon United States

The preliminary dataset was derived from 135 Amazon reviews across five regions: Australia, Germany, India, Italy, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, and the United States. Figure 2 demonstrates some exemplary Amazon reviews. The data generation process involved three main steps:

1) *Identifying variables proxying love and representing characteristics of the book*

Variables representing love and the factors influencing readers' emotional connection with the book were identified by carefully analyzing the reviews. This process continued until theoretical saturation was reached. Given that love is a multi-faceted concept with no universally agreed-upon definition (Fehr & Russell, 1991; Reis & Aron, 2008; Thumala Olave, 2020, 2022), the study adopted a practical approach by using proxies for love, focusing on words and behaviors reflecting emotional attachment and commitment.

- Emotional attachment was identified through keywords such as “love,” “gem,” “masterpiece,” “treasure,” “heartwarming,” “mesmerizing,” “resonate,” “inspire,” and “captivating.”
- Commitment was inferred from descriptions of behaviors like sharing the book with others and re-reading it.

 Bright Chapter Production

★★★★★ **Kingfisher's Whimsical Adventures**

Reviewed in the United States on December 19, 2024

Charming collection of tales set in a whimsical village where animals speak and each day is filled with delightful surprises. The standout character, Kingfisher, embarks on humorous and heartfelt adventures with his fellow villagers, blending fun with deeper reflections on life and society.

Vuong's storytelling is imaginative and rich with cultural nuances, offering readers a unique blend of humor, wisdom, and thoughtful insights. While some tales may feel fantastical for those preferring straightforward narratives, this book is perfect for readers seeking creative, lighthearted stories with a touch of sagacity.

Helpful

Report

Sandra Jessop

★★★★★ **Thought-Provoking, Humorous, and Uniquely Captivating**

Reviewed in the United States on December 19, 2024

This collection of stories is an absolute delight, offering a perfect blend of humor, whimsy, and deep reflection. Set in a fantastical bird village, the tales of Kingfisher bring snippets of Vietnamese culture to life while delivering timeless, universal wisdom. Quan-Hoang Vuong's writing is playful yet insightful, much like traditional fables, but with a distinctly modern and satirical twist that makes them feel fresh and relevant.

Each story, though short and snappy, packs a punch—providing entertainment while gently nudging readers to reflect on human nature, society, and the values we hold dear. The clever social commentary feels both lighthearted and profound, a rare balance that makes this book truly stand out. With beautiful illustrations to complement the stories, this collection is a joy to read and leaves a lasting impression. Highly recommended for anyone who enjoys fables, humor, and a touch of cultural exploration.

Helpful

Report

Bob Thompson

★★★★★ **Different and fun**

Reviewed in the United States on December 18, 2024

A compilation of Kingfisher tales, this is an interesting book that combines fun and contemplative moments in a quaint village. The main character is Kingfisher, a bird who embarks on misadventures with other village dwellers. I like that the author has continued to add new stories when new editions are published.

Helpful

Report

Figure 2. Amazon reviews of *Wild Wise Weird*

2) Data collection

A Google Forms questionnaire was designed to capture the identified variables along with meta-information about each review, including the review's date, location, title, text, and reviewer name. This questionnaire was then used to evaluate the reviews systematically. Four co-authors were responsible for evaluating and entering the data. Upon completion of the initial data collection, the same co-authors cross-checked the entries to ensure data reliability and consistency. In cases of discrepancies, the co-authors discussed the inconsistencies collaboratively to determine the most accurate and valid input.

Besides the variable proxying love for the book, the questionnaire also helps collect variables representing characteristics of the book, namely: *Humor*, *UniqueInnovativeness*, *Nostalgia*, *WitWise*, *Painting*, *Characters*, *ThoughtProvoking*, *CulturalRepresentativeness*, *SocialCommentary*, and *ValuesLessons*. Detailed descriptions of these variables are presented in Table 1.

3) Data curation and validation

During this phase, reviews that were too short or lacked substantive information were excluded to ensure data quality. This refinement process led to the removal of six unqualified observations, resulting in a final dataset of 129 reviews for subsequent analysis.

Table 1. Variables' description

Variables	Description	Type of variable	Value
<i>Love</i>	Whether the reader has an emotional connection and commitment to the book	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0
<i>Humor</i>	Whether the reader thinks the book is humorous or funny	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0

<i>UniqueInnovativeness</i>	Whether the reader thinks the book is unique, innovative, creative, quirky, or whimsical	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0
<i>Nostalgia</i>	Whether the book makes the reader sentimental about past events or objects (e.g., moments reading a book with father)	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0
<i>WitWise</i>	Whether the reader thinks the book is witty, wise, or intelligent	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0
<i>Painting</i>	Whether the reader thinks the book has appealing paintings	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0
<i>Characters</i>	Whether the reader thinks the book's characters are appealing	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0
<i>ThoughtProvoking</i>	Whether the reader thinks the book is thought-provoking, prompting reflection, or contemplation	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0
<i>CulturalRepresentativeness</i>	Whether the reader thinks the book is culturally rich and representative	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0
<i>SocialCommentary</i>	Whether the reader thinks the book is a social commentary	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0
<i>ValuesLessons</i>	Whether the reader thinks the book provides life lessons,	Binary	Yes = 1 No = 0

	humanistic values, and wisdom		
--	----------------------------------	--	--

The validated dataset was analyzed using the **bayesvl** package built on the R platform, which utilizes the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm for estimation (La & Vuong, 2019). The constructed model is as follows:

2.2.2. Statistical model

The following model was constructed to examine the effects of a book's characteristics on a reader's love for the book:

$$Love \sim normal\left(\log\left(\frac{\mu_i}{1-\mu_i}\right), \sigma\right) \quad (1.1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \log\left(\frac{\mu_i}{1-\mu_i}\right) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 * Humor_i + \beta_2 * UniqueInnovativeness_i + \beta_3 * \\ & Nostalgia_i + \beta_4 * WitWise_i + \beta_5 * Painting_i + \beta_6 * Characters_i + \\ & \beta_7 * ThoughtProvoking_i + \beta_8 * CulturalRepresentativeness_i + \beta_9 * \\ & SocialCommentary_i + \beta_{10} * ValuesLessons_i \end{aligned} \quad (1.2)$$

$$\beta \sim normal(M, S) \quad (1.3)$$

The probability around the mean $\log\left(\frac{\mu_i}{1-\mu_i}\right)$ is determined by the form of the normal distribution, whose width is specified by the standard deviation σ . μ_i indicates the reader i 's probability of having an emotional connection or commitment to the book. Model 1 has twelve parameters: the coefficients, $\beta_1 - \beta_{10}$, the intercept, β_0 , and the standard deviation of the "noise", σ . The coefficients of the predictor variables are distributed normally around the mean, denoted M , and with the standard deviation, denoted S . Figure 3 below presents the logical network of the constructed model.

Figure 3. Constructed the model's logical network

2.3. Analysis and validation

Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics was employed for several reasons (Vuong et al., 2022). First, the analytical method integrates the logical reasoning capabilities of GITT with the inferential advantages of Bayesian analysis, exhibiting a high degree of compatibility (Nguyen et al., 2022). Second, Bayesian inference is a statistical approach that treats all the properties (including the known and unknown ones) probabilistically (Csilléry et al., 2010; Gill, 2014), enabling the reliable prediction of parsimonious models. Nevertheless, utilizing the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) technique still allows Bayesian analysis to deal effectively with various intricate models, such as multilevel and nonlinear regression frameworks (Dunson, 2001). Third, Bayesian inference utilizes credible intervals for result interpretation instead of relying solely on the dichotomous decision based on p -values (Halsey et al., 2015; Wagenmakers et al., 2018).

In Bayesian analysis, selecting the appropriate prior is required during the model construction process. Due to the exploratory nature of this study, uninformative priors or a flat prior distribution were used to provide as little prior information as possible for model estimation (Diaconis & Ylvisaker, 1985). To check the estimation's robustness, we also

reran the model using informative priors reflecting our disbelief in the effects of the book's characteristics on readers' love. If the estimated results remain similar to those estimated using uninformative priors, the results can be considered insensitive to prior beliefs.

In addition, we also employed the Pareto-smoothed importance sampling leave-one-out (PSIS-LOO) diagnostics to check the models' goodness-of-fit (Vehtari & Gabry, 2019; Vehtari et al., 2017). LOO is computed as follows:

$$LOO = -2LPPD_{loo} = -2 \sum_{i=1}^n \log \int p(y_i|\theta)p_{post(-i)}(\theta)d\theta$$

$p_{post(-i)}(\theta)$ is the posterior distribution calculated through the data minus the data point i . The k -Pareto values are used in the PSIS method to compute the LOO cross-validation in the R `loo` package. Observations with k -Pareto values greater than 0.7 are often considered influential and problematic for accurately estimating LOO cross-validation. When a model's k values are less than 0.5, it is typically regarded as being fit.

If the model fits well with the data, we will proceed with the convergence diagnoses and result interpretation. In the current study, we validated the convergence of Markov chains using statistical values and visual illustrations. Statistically, the effective sample size (n_{eff}) and the Gelman–Rubin shrink factor ($Rhat$) can be used to assess the convergence. The n_{eff} value represents the number of iterative samples that are not autocorrelated during stochastic simulation, while the $Rhat$ value is referred to as the potential scale reduction factor (Brooks & Gelman, 1998). If n_{eff} is larger than 1000, it is generally considered that the Markov chains are well-convergent, and the effective samples are sufficient for reliable inference (McElreath, 2018). As for the $Rhat$ value, if the value exceeds 1.1, the model does not converge. The model is considered convergent if $Rhat = 1$. Visually, the Markov chains' convergence was validated using trace plots, Gelman–Rubin–Brooks plots, and autocorrelation plots.

To complement the interpretation of the quantitative results and enhance their comprehensiveness, we also included illustrative qualitative Amazon reviews that reflect the characteristics influencing readers' expressions of love. These reviews were selected based on three criteria: (1) relevance to the key patterns identified in the quantitative analysis; (2) the review is self-contained and sufficiently rich in content; and (3) the selected reviews convey distinct perspectives to ensure maximum variation and avoid redundancy.

For the sake of research transparency and reducing research and reproducibility costs, we have stored all data and computer code on Zenodo: [Anonymized].

3. Results

Prior to analyzing the results, it is essential to evaluate the goodness of fit of Model 1 in relation to the data. As illustrated in Figure 4, all the estimated k -values fall below the 0.5 threshold, suggesting a good alignment between the model and the data.

Figure 4. Model 1's PSIS-LOO diagnosis

The statistical analysis of the posterior distributions for Model 1 is presented in Table 1. All effective sample size (n_{eff}) values well exceed 1000, and the $Rhat$ values are equal to 1, indicating that the Markov chains for Model 1 exhibit strong convergence. This convergence is further illustrated by the trace plots in Figure 5, where it is evident that

the values of all chains stabilize around a central equilibrium following the 2000th iteration (after the warmup phase).

Table 2. Estimated results of Model 1

Parameters	Uninformative priors				Informative priors			
	Mean	SD	<i>n_eff</i>	<i>Rhat</i>	Mean	SD	<i>n_eff</i>	<i>Rhat</i>
<i>Constant</i>	-0.71	0.53	12617	1	-0.64	0.52	11465	1
<i>Humor</i>	-0.02	0.58	12074	1	0.02	0.55	12525	1
<i>UniqueInnovativeness</i>	0.79	0.46	13359	1	0.74	0.44	14632	1
<i>Nostalgia</i>	0.37	0.93	14138	1	0.33	0.85	12857	1
<i>WitWise</i>	0.01	0.48	14616	1	0.03	0.47	14652	1
<i>Painting</i>	0.78	0.78	12747	1	0.69	0.71	12922	1
<i>Characters</i>	1.47	0.55	15093	1	1.35	0.51	15821	1
<i>ThoughtProvoking</i>	-0.27	0.62	13358	1	-0.24	0.57	11282	1
<i>CulturalRepresentativeness</i>	1.00	0.49	11483	1	0.93	0.48	12325	1
<i>SocialCommentary</i>	-0.08	0.51	13482	1	-0.06	0.48	13252	1
<i>ValuesLesson</i>	0.45	0.53	13444	1	0.41	0.50	11524	1

Figure 5. Model 1's trace plots

Figure 6. Model 1's Gelman-Rubin-Brooks plots

The Gelman-Rubin-Brooks diagnostic plots, along with the autocorrelation plots, indicate a favorable convergence of the Markov chains. The Gelman-Rubin-Brooks plots are employed to evaluate the ratio of variance between different Markov chains to the variance within individual chains. The y -axis represents the shrink factor (or Gelman-Rubin factor), while the x -axis illustrates the sequence of iterations in the simulation. In Figure 6, the shrink factors for all parameters decrease sharply to 1 prior to the 2000th iteration (during the warmup phase). This observation implies that there is no divergence present among the Markov chains.

Figure 7. Model 1's autocorrelation plots

The Markov property denotes the characteristic of a stochastic process that is devoid of memory. In essence, the values generated in each iteration exhibit no autocorrelation with preceding iteration values. Autocorrelation plots are utilized to assess the levels of autocorrelation present among these iteration values. The graphs depicted in Figure 7 illustrate the mean autocorrelation of each Markov chain on the y -axis, with the lag of the chains represented on the x -axis. Observationally, the autocorrelation levels of all Markov chains rapidly diminish to zero after a limited number of lags (specifically, prior to 5), indicating that the Markov property is satisfied and that the Markov chains demonstrate strong convergence.

Since all the diagnostics confirm the convergence of Markov chains, the simulated results are eligible for interpretation. In a review analysis of 129 Amazon entries for *Wild Wise Weird*, approximately 66% of respondents express emotional attachment and

commitment to the book, with various factors influencing their love for the book. The estimated results of Model 1 show that readers who describe the book as unique and innovative, and cultural richness/representativeness are more likely to express love for the book ($M_{UniqueInnovativeness} = 0.79$ and $S_{UniqueInnovativeness} = 0.46$; $M_{CulturalRepresentativeness} = 1.00$ and $S_{CulturalRepresentativeness} = 0.49$).

Figure 8 displays the posterior distributions, with the thick blue line representing 95% Highest Posterior Density Intervals (HPDIs). These intervals capture the regions of highest posterior probability, meaning they contain the most credible values for the parameter estimates given the data and prior. In essence, any point within the HPDI is more likely than any point outside the interval. The reliability of the association between predictor and outcome variables can be assessed by examining the HPDIs in conjunction with the difference between the mean and standard deviation of the coefficients. An association is considered highly reliable when the HPDI lies entirely or predominantly on one side of the origin (i.e., strictly positive or strictly negative). If the HPDI crosses the origin, the reliability is further evaluated based on the ratio of the absolute mean to the standard deviation: the association is highly reliable when the absolute mean is substantially larger than the standard deviation, moderately reliable when the two are approximately equal, and weakly reliable when the absolute mean is smaller than the standard deviation.

As can be seen in Figure 6, the distribution of *CulturalRepresentativeness* is located entirely on the positive side of the x-axis, suggesting the high reliability of the results. While a portion of *UniqueInnovativeness*'s distribution is located on the negative side, that portion is negligible, and its mean value ($M_{UniqueInnovativeness}$) is much larger than its standard deviation value ($S_{UniqueInnovativeness}$), so the positive effect of *UniqueInnovativeness* can still be deemed highly reliable. The following review exemplifies these results well:

“Just brilliant guys! This is a captivating anthology of short stories originally written in Vietnamese. The book centres around the protagonist, Kingfisher, and introduces readers to snippets of Vietnamese culture through the humorous and satirical life of the bird village. I didn't know Vietnamese culture is so good. The stories have whimsical, wise, and strange elements, offering adventures, life lessons, and unique stuff. This collection is perfect for fans of fantasy and the surreal, providing both

entertainment and thought-provoking content. Overall, I would recommend this book.”

“A splendid read!” — An assessment of a reader in the United Kingdom

Figure 8. Model 1's posterior distributions

Moreover, readers who are attracted by the paintings and the characters in the book are found to be more likely to express love for the book ($M_{Painting} = 0.78$ and $S_{Painting} = 0.78$; $M_{Characters} = 1.47$ and $S_{Characters} = 0.55$). The entire HPDI of *Characters* is located on the positive side, suggesting high reliability. Meanwhile, although a proportion of *Painting's* distribution is located on the negative side, its mean value is equal to its standard deviation, so the reliability of the positive effect can be deemed moderate. The following review can demonstrate these findings well:

“The enchanting cover of "Wild Wise Weird: The Kingfisher Story Collection" immediately drew me in, the vivid image of the kingfisher beckoning me into a world filled with rich stories. And rich they truly are. Author Quan-Hoang Vuong has masterfully crafted a collection of captivating fables, each with its own unique charm and moral lesson.

Like ancient tales passed down through generations, Vuong's stories evoke a sense of wonder and connection to our collective cultural heritage. They utilize symbolism, humor, and cleverly crafted animal characters to deliver timeless truths in ways that resonate deeply, no matter your age. While some might see the genre as outdated, the power of these fables lies in their ability to hold a mirror to human behavior and explore universal themes that transcend time and culture.

One of the strengths of this collection is its ability to seamlessly weave the traditional elements of fables with modern sensibility. Each story offers a fresh perspective while retaining the essence of this ancient form of storytelling. I was completely absorbed in each tale, engrossed in the beautifully detailed narrative, captivated by the lessons imparted, and charmed by the unique personality of each animal character. "Wild Wise Weird: The Kingfisher Story Collection" is a must-read for those looking for a delightful escape into a world of captivating storytelling, imbued with wisdom, humor, and heart.”

“A Captivating Dive into the World of Fables: A Review of "Wild Wise Weird”
— An assessment of a reader in the United States

The estimated results using informative priors reflecting our disbelief in the associations do not show any different tendencies from the estimated results employing uninformative priors. Hence, the findings can be deemed robust against changing priors.

4. Discussion

This study looks at the factors that influence readers’ love for the book, or more specifically, their emotional attachment to a fiction book, focusing on how elements like unique innovativeness, emotional engagement, aesthetic appeal, cultural representation, and humor work together to create strong connections. By analyzing Amazon reviews of *Wild Wise Weird* using the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF), the study examines how these elements combine to shape readers’ love for the book.

4.1. The multi-faceted appeal of *Wild Wise Weird*

4.1.1. Uniqueness and innovation

In *Wild Wise Weird*, the book's unique storytelling approach plays a pivotal role in fostering readers' emotional connection to the narrative. The book's central appeal lies in its capacity to illuminate the absurdities of human thought through its characters, encouraging readers to engage in self-reflection and independently derive insights about wisdom and meaning. This narrative approach remains ideologically neutral and transcends specific social or cultural boundaries, and focuses on individual information processing (Nguyen, 2024). By fostering such introspective and interpretive processes, the book contributes to the cultivation of the reader's Nature Quotient (NQ)—a cognitive capacity to perceive, process, and organize information concerning the interrelations and dynamic interactions among complex information-processing systems, including the self and the broader environment (Vuong & Nguyen, 2025). This philosophical sensibility and the minimal sense of humor are reminiscent of classical Daoist thinkers such as Laozi (老子) and Zhuangzi (莊子), whose work similarly invited readers to navigate paradoxes and embrace epistemic humility. As Laozi famously quoted: "When the people of the world all know beauty as beauty, there arises the recognition of ugliness. When they all know the good as good, there arises the recognition of evil." This statement reflects a core thematic resonance: wisdom arises not from asserting fixed meanings but from remaining attuned to the ever-shifting interplay of reality, values, perceptions, and lived experiences. This subtlety enhances the emotional resonance, making the characters and their world more relatable and accessible (Tran, 2025).

By framing its social commentary and satire in a lighthearted manner, the book further strengthens readers' emotional attachment. This playful tone allows the social commentary to integrate seamlessly into the narrative, deepening readers' connection to the story while encouraging a more personal and reflective engagement with its themes. This approach sets the book apart from genres like dystopian fiction, where social critique—on topics such as government control—often takes center stage, engaging readers primarily on an intellectual level (Campbell, 2019; Jones & Paris, 2018).

The author's distinctive style also shines by offering fresh perspectives and crafting a new reading experience in a crowded literary landscape. By blending social commentary with anthropomorphic characters—such as the memorable Kingfisher—set in a vibrant bird village, the book seamlessly combines imaginative storytelling with profound reflections

on human society. This duality invites readers to engage in an experience that is both entertaining and thought-provoking.

The book's innovative approach reflects a broader trend in literature, emphasizing how unique and original stories can resonate with readers on both intellectual and emotional levels. Research indicates that stories providing a balance of intellectual stimulation and emotional depth are more likely to forge strong reader connections (Ahmed et al., 2024; Bouizegarene et al., 2024). *Wild Wise Weird* achieves this equilibrium by integrating social and philosophical themes, engaging the mind while provoking emotional responses. By merging creativity with fables, the author deepens readers' engagement with the characters and the intricately crafted world they inhabit.

In today's competitive literary market, innovation is essential for standing out. The book's combination of traditional fables with contemporary themes offers a fresh perspective that appeals to a diverse audience. This approach—melding timeless narratives with modern issues—recalls the works of authors like George Orwell and Aziz Nesin, who employed creative storytelling to examine societal themes (Nesin, 2002; Orwell, 2021). By addressing contemporary topics such as technology and climate change through a fable-inspired lens, *Wild Wise Weird* contributes to the ongoing evolution of literature. It exemplifies how innovative narrative can offer fresh insights into universal human experiences, enriching the literary canon while capturing the complexities of our modern world.

The literary market is poised to become increasingly competitive with the rise of artificial intelligence. As AI-generated books proliferate—driven by significant reductions in labor, time, and production costs—the literary landscape is being rapidly flooded with shallow content (Ho & Ho, 2025). In the weeks following the release of ChatGPT, self-publishing platforms like Amazon's Kindle Direct Publishing saw a surge of hundreds of new titles authored or co-authored using AI tools (Cuthbertson, 2023). This surge brings with it a growing uniformity in narrative style and thematic execution. Many AI-generated texts tend to converge toward formulaic patterns, resulting in works that are less original and creatively distinctive (Brodsky, 2024; Chayka, 2025).

At the same time, AI is not only reshaping the production side of literature but is also being progressively integrated into how readers engage with books, informing decisions about what to read, how to evaluate content, and how to compare works across genres and authors (Ho & Vuong, 2025). As a case in point, we conducted an exploratory

experiment using Microsoft Copilot to assess the timeless qualities of *Wild Wise Weird*, drawing a comparative lens with George Orwell’s *Animal Farm* and Aziz Nesin’s *Laugh or Lament*. The AI-generated response is presented in Box 1 below. This example illustrates how AI tools can be employed as exploratory instruments that enrich contemporary reading practices and literary discourse.

Within this rapidly evolving context, uniqueness and narrative innovation are becoming critical markers of literary value. As the volume of content increases and AI-produced texts converge stylistically, works that offer novel perspectives, distinctive voice, and imaginative storytelling will be more likely to stand out (Horton Jr et al., 2023; Wielded, 2024). Thus, the creative differentiation of literary works—both in content and in interpretive framing—will play a pivotal role in capturing and sustaining reader engagement in the age of algorithmically generated literature.

Box 1. Microsoft Copilot’s answer regarding the timelessness of *Wild Wise Weird* in comparison to George Orwell’s *Animal Farm* and Aziz Nesin’s *Laugh or Lament*

<p>Prompt:</p> <p>Does <i>Wild Wise Weird</i> have timelessness characteristics like <i>Animal Farm</i> and <i>Laugh or Lament</i>?</p>
<p>Microsoft Copilot’s answer:</p> <p>Absolutely! Let's explore how “Wild Wise Weird” compares in timelessness with “Animal Farm” by George Orwell and “Laugh or Lament: Selected Short Stories” by Aziz Nesin:</p> <p>Timeless Characteristics of “Wild Wise Weird”:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Universal Themes:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Focuses on wisdom, human behavior, and environmental awareness, which are always relevant and impactful across different eras.2. Narrative Style:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Uses fables with moral lessons, a storytelling method that has endured through centuries and remains appealing to various generations.

3. Cultural Relevance:

- While containing cultural nuances specific to Vietnam, the core messages are universally relatable, making the collection accessible and relevant over time.

Timeless Characteristics of “Animal Farm”:

1. Universal Themes:

- Explores the nature of power, corruption, and political oppression, which are perennially relevant as they reflect ongoing political dynamics.

2. Allegory:

- The use of allegory allows it to be applicable to various political contexts beyond its original reference to the Russian Revolution and the early Soviet Union.

3. Global Impact:

- Widely studied and adapted, influencing political discourse globally, ensuring its longevity.

Timeless Characteristics of “Laugh or Lament: Selected Short Stories”:

1. Universal Themes:

- Addresses social injustices, bureaucratic absurdities, and human folly, topics that remain pertinent across different societies and times.

2. Humor and Satire:

- Uses humor and satire to critique societal issues, a timeless approach that resonates with readers who appreciate wit and social commentary.

3. Cultural Relevance:

- Reflects Turkish society, yet the absurdities and injustices depicted are universally recognizable, making the stories relatable to a global audience.

Comparisons and Differences:

1. Themes:

- **Wild Wise Weird:** Wisdom, human nature, environmental awareness.
- **Animal Farm:** Power, corruption, political satire.
- **Laugh or Lament:** Social injustice, bureaucracy, human folly.

2. Tone and Style:

- **Wild Wise Weird:** Humorous and satirical, focusing on moral lessons through fables.
- **Animal Farm:** Somber and allegorical, critiquing political systems.
- **Laugh or Lament:** Humorous and satirical, exposing societal flaws.

3. Cultural Influence:

- **Wild Wise Weird:** Contains cultural nuances specific to Vietnam, but with universally relatable messages.
- **Animal Farm:** Has a global impact, is widely studied, and has been adapted.
- **Laugh or Lament:** Reflects Turkish society, yet its themes are universally recognizable.

While each work has its unique context and style, they all share the ability to address fundamental human experiences and societal issues in a way that resonates across different times and cultures. “**Wild Wise Weird**” stands alongside “**Animal Farm**” and “**Laugh or Lament**” in its timelessness, offering enduring lessons and reflections through its satirical fables.

4.1.2. Characters and paintings

In *Wild Wise Weird*, emotional engagement operates much like the formation of love between people—a complex and multi-faceted experience that transcends mere physical actions. From a biological standpoint, emotional connections arise through intricate brain processes and the release of chemicals such as oxytocin, dopamine, and serotonin (De Boer et al., 2012). These mechanisms shape the various relationships we form, whether romantic, familial, or platonic. Similarly, the book’s storytelling creates a profound emotional bond with readers by focusing on richly developed characters and immersive sensory experiences of paintings (see Figure 9).

The book's vivid and detailed writing draws readers into the world of the story, fostering a deep emotional connection. Just as the brain's emotional responses help people bond with others, the book's evocative descriptions elicit emotions that pull readers into the narrative. The nature imagery and symbolic elements of the bird village enhance this connection, cultivating a serene and reflective mood. This sensory and emotional resonance parallels the way feelings of affection grow in real-life relationships (Hartung et al., 2021). Through skillful world-building, *Wild Wise Weird* enables readers to form enduring emotional ties with the characters and themes of the book (Olf et al., 2013).

Figure 9. Watercolor painting by Bui Quang Khiem in *Wild Wise Weird*

The storytelling, when combined with paintings, also aligns with the concept of multimodal engagement, which suggests that sensory details paired with a good narrative enhance emotional involvement (Theresia & Recard, 2021). The sensory richness of *Wild Wise Weird*—its vivid descriptions of sights, sounds, and textures, as well as appealing paintings—bridges the gap between the reader’s imagination and the fictional world. This immersive experience mirrors the emotional bonding we experience in personal relationships. By engaging multiple senses, Vuong deepens the emotional impact of the narrative, allowing readers to connect on a profound level (Winkler et al., 2023).

A cornerstone of this emotional connection lies in the book’s well-developed characters, particularly Kingfisher. Representing wisdom, vulnerability, and the shared struggles of human existence, Kingfisher resonates deeply with readers. His relatable qualities and emotional journey reflect the complexities of human relationships, fostering empathy and a sense of shared experience. This aligns with narrative engagement theories, which emphasize how relatable characters enhance emotional attachment and empathy (Bae et al., 2014). Through the Kingfisher and the broader narrative, the author crafts a story that not only entertains but also profoundly connects with readers on a human level.

4.1.3. Cultural representativeness

Wild Wise Weird exemplifies the growing importance of cultural representation in contemporary literature. As interest in diverse voices grows, scholars like Altun (2023) and Akhter (2020) argue that literature should reflect the diversity of human experiences. The book does this successfully by blending elements of Vietnamese culture with universal themes. This mix allows readers to connect with both shared human experiences and specific cultural traditions, creating a deeper understanding and empathy for different cultural perspectives.

One of the strengths of *Wild Wise Weird*’s storytelling is how the book balances cultural details with a broader appeal. By incorporating Vietnamese folklore into themes like identity, morality, and resilience, *Wild Wise Weird* offers readers a unique insight into a culture that is rarely highlighted in mainstream literature. Research on cross-cultural

exchange suggests that books like this can open doors for readers to engage with perspectives that are different from their own, fostering a deeper appreciation for cultural diversity.

In a literary world where Eurocentric narratives often dominate (Gwekwerere, 2018), the book with nuances from Vietnamese culture provides a refreshing and important alternative. The symbolic animals and nature-based storytelling, inspired by Vietnamese folklore, are skillfully integrated into the plot. These elements are not only a key part of the book's cultural richness but also tie into universal themes like personal growth and community. Through the character of Kingfisher and the context of the bird village, the book introduces readers to aspects of Vietnamese culture that feel both relevant to broader human experiences and uniquely tied to the story's setting.

By seamlessly blending cultural representation with universal themes, the author creates a story that resonates with diverse audiences while celebrating the unique richness of Vietnam. This careful balance between cultural specificity and accessibility fosters a deeper and more meaningful connection with the book. Additionally, it effectively conveys the depth, charm, and moral essence of Vietnamese culture to global audiences. Its success is reflected in the fact that some readers even said "thank you" in their reviews to express their gratitude after finishing the book.

"I love how the author integrated Vietnamese culture through the Kingfisher. Very cool way to keep a reader engaged while making it funny and interesting to listen to! A very refreshing read, thank you."

"A lovely way to spread culture through birds!"
— An assessment of a reader in Canada

4.2. The intellectual and emotional engagement conundrum

Beyond the clear positive associations between readers' love for *Wild Wise Weird* and characteristics such as uniqueness, innovation, appealing characters, paintings, and cultural richness, the analysis also uncovers a set of ambiguous associations. Characteristics such as humor, social commentary, thought-provoking content, wit, wisdom, intellectual depth, and value lessons ambiguously predict emotional attachment to the book. This inconclusiveness underscores a potential dilemma: while these elements stimulate cognitive engagement, they do not necessarily foster emotional connection or commitment.

When a book emphasizes intellectual narratives—such as social commentary, thought-provoking content, value reflection, or intellectual depth—readers may adopt a more analytical rather than emotional stance. Such engagement can interrupt narrative transportation, the immersive experience of being “lost” in the story, which is a key mechanism in emotional attachment. Attributes like wit or wisdom may impress readers intellectually, yet admiration is not always synonymous with affection. From the perspective of aesthetic distance, these forms of intellectual engagement can serve as distancing cues, encouraging readers to reflect on the story critically rather than emotionally experience it. This aligns with Brecht’s *Verfremdungseffekt* (distancing or alienation effect), which renders readers as observers who remain emotionally detached, enabling them to comprehend the absurdities within the stories intellectually rather than sympathize with their characters (Brecht et al., 1961; Nguyen, 2024).

According to GITT, emotional attachment arises when narrative information is meaningfully absorbed into a reader’s mind, generating affective micro-responses—such as empathy, joy, or excitement—that reinforce perceived value. While intellectual content may reduce narrative ambiguity (or entropy) and stimulate reflective thought, it is often not sufficient to yield these affective responses that are essential for love. Keen (2006) similarly emphasizes the role of narrative empathy—the vicarious, spontaneous sharing of affect—as central to emotional connection. When elements such as thought-provoking insights, intellectual depth, social reflection, and philosophical contemplation dominate, they may crowd out affective resonance, leaving readers intellectually appreciative but emotionally disengaged. In such cases, the book is more likely to be perceived as a teacher or commentator rather than a companion that evokes emotional connections.

Nostalgia also ambiguously predicts book love. Though it can evoke warmth and sentimentality, nostalgia is often a highly individualized and fleeting emotion. Research describes it as a “bittersweet” feeling, rooted in personal memory and prone to diminishing emotional returns over time (Layous et al., 2022; Sedikides et al., 2015). In GITT terms, nostalgia needs to contribute new emotional insight and integrate with the reader’s evolving mindset to foster love. If nostalgic cues merely echo personal memories—such as recalling moments of childhood reading—they may generate pleasant sentiment, but not a durable attachment to

the book itself. Furthermore, if those memories do not align across readers or resonate with the narrative content, their emotional salience may become diluted.

Humor presents a similar case. While readers often value humor and find it enjoyable, its emotional impact tends to be ephemeral. Amusement and laughter produce short-term positive affect but rarely accumulate into the kind of deep-seated meaning-making that supports long-term emotional connection. Moreover, comedic devices—particularly satire—may increase aesthetic distance, positioning the reader as an amused observer rather than an empathic participant. This distancing, again, may inhibit the development of emotional connection and narrative empathy.

Collectively, these findings highlight a central dilemma in literary reception: intellectual appreciation does not necessarily equate to emotional attachment. From a GITT perspective, love is a subjective, emergent output of sustained cognitive-affective interactions between narrative inputs and the reader's value system. Characteristics that stimulate thought—wit, philosophy, satire, or commentary—can reduce informational entropy and provide narrative insight, aiding readers in interpreting societal themes or discerning authorial intent. However, if these cognitive pathways do not sufficiently elicit affective micro-responses, they are unlikely to foster the kind of personal value synthesis that gives rise to love or sustained emotional commitment to the book. When readers are prompted to engage primarily through critical reflection—particularly in response to satire or social commentary—they may adopt the role of detached spectators rather than immersive participants in the fictional world.

This intellectual–emotional dilemma invites deeper reflection on both literary design and reader expectations. Books that aim to be thought-provoking or intellectually sharp may impress readers cognitively but often fall short of cultivating lasting emotional bonds unless they also evoke affective proximity. In contrast, emotionally rich features—such as relatable characters, evocative illustrations, or cultural resonance—tend to more effectively bridge the aesthetic gap, appealing directly to the reader's inner emotional world and identity-relevant values. In this light, the dilemma is not merely a narrative challenge but a theoretical conundrum: how can literature simultaneously serve as a vehicle for intellectual understanding and emotional connection? The answer may lie in

crafting literary experiences that do not sacrifice emotional depth for cognitive sophistication, but instead harmonize the two through affective meaning-making, which can transform not only how readers think, but how they feel.

4.3. Strategies for captivating readers and enhancing global reach

4.3.1. Prioritizing originality and creative storytelling

In today's oversaturated literary market, findings from this study suggest that authors should prioritize originality and creative storytelling to capture readers' attention (Kent, 2015). This requires experimenting with unconventional narratives, incorporating unexpected plot twists, and offering fresh perspectives, often by blending genres or challenging traditional tropes. Crafting relatable and symbolic characters is also helpful for fostering emotional connections, as well-developed characters with clear motivations, flaws, and universal themes tend to leave a lasting impact. Research suggests that readers form emotional bonds with characters through empathy, engagement, and identification (Denham, 2024; Parsons, 2013), making character development central to creating immersive experiences.

In addition to strong characters, vivid descriptions, and sensory details can significantly enhance immersion, inviting readers to feel as though they are truly part of the world being created. Descriptive writing—whether visual, auditory, or sensory, combined with appealing visualizations, illustrations, or paintings, helps ground readers in the story, making it more engaging and emotionally resonant (Koliada & Kalynovska, 2023; Salih, 2024). Furthermore, authors should consider cultural authenticity and diversity in their work. By incorporating elements of cultural diversity—whether through setting, character identity, or themes—authors can create engaging narratives that resonate with readers and stand out in a competitive market. Ultimately, the blend of originality, relatable characters, vivid descriptions, and cultural exploration plays a vital role in creating stories that resonate with a diverse audience.

4.3.2. Enhancing marketing strategies for publishers

To succeed in today's competitive literary market, publishers should prioritize originality and aesthetic appeal in their storytelling and presentation. This includes developing unique narratives, engaging characters, and captivating book designs that attract diverse audiences (Brown, 2011). By focusing on character-driven stories that forge emotional

connections, publishers can deepen readers' engagement, ensuring that the book resonates on a personal level (Johnson & Simpson, 2022). However, to maximize the impact of marketing, publishers need to understand their audience beyond just sales data better, utilizing direct feedback and surveys to fine-tune campaigns. Additionally, using social media platforms like Instagram and TikTok can create ongoing relationships with readers and expand the book's visibility in a crowded market.

This study demonstrates the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) as an innovative and effective method for exploring and assessing the value of a book using data from online platforms like Amazon. The framework is not only flexible but also cost-effective, as it utilizes R, an open-source software, for all analyses. This makes BMF a practical and accessible tool for replicating and quantitatively analyzing other books and genres. Additionally, the study provides reusable scripts, enabling researchers and analysts to adopt and apply this approach easily in future analyses.

4.3.3. Incorporating cultural depth to connect with a global audience

The growing demand for diverse perspectives in literature calls for publishers to focus on cultural richness as a core strategy. As readers become more globally conscious, books that feature diverse cultural narratives and reflect a variety of experiences resonate deeply with modern audiences (Garces-Bacsal, 2022). Publishers can take advantage of this opportunity by promoting underrepresented voices and exploring universal themes through culturally specific perspectives. The ability to localize content and collaborate with international distributors can expand a book's reach to diverse markets, while social media platforms like Amazon, Goodreads, and Instagram offer key opportunities to increase a book's visibility across cultures. By prioritizing cultural inclusivity alongside strong storytelling, publishers can strengthen their brand and appeal to a broader, more diverse readership.

4.4. Limitations and future research directions

The study is not without limitations. This study's focus on reviews of a single book limits the generalizability of its findings to other contexts or genres. Emotional keywords used to assess engagement may oversimplify readers' responses, overlooking subtler connections. These limitations underscore the need for caution in applying the findings broadly and highlight opportunities for more expansive research.

Future studies could expand on the present findings by incorporating a broader range of literary genres and more diverse reader demographics to gain a deeper understanding of emotional engagement across different forms of fiction. Extending the analysis to genres such as romance, science fiction, historical fiction, or literary fiction could help determine whether the emotional drivers identified in this study—such as perceptions of uniqueness, illustrations, and cultural richness—are genre-specific or broadly applicable across fiction types. In addition, the use of mixed methods, including interviews and focus groups, would allow for deeper exploration of the cognitive and emotional mechanisms behind reader attachment. Such qualitative approaches could complement textual analysis and provide richer insights into how readers interpret and internalize stories.

Cross-cultural comparative research is also encouraged to examine how readers' cultural backgrounds influence emotional engagement. Specifically, such studies could investigate how cultural proximity or distance mediates attachment to fiction. This is especially relevant for culturally rich works like *Wild Wise Weird*, which conveys Vietnamese cultural nuances to a global audience. Future research could explore whether readers from culturally proximate backgrounds experience deeper emotional resonance due to shared values and symbols, or whether cultural novelty itself fosters curiosity and emotional connection.

Longitudinal studies offer another important direction. Tracking changes in readers' emotional responses over time—such as by comparing initial reviews with later reflections or reread experiences—would help illuminate how emotional attachment evolves. This approach could capture shifts in memory, emotional engagement, and the perceived meaning of a text as readers' perspectives change.

While Amazon reviews offer a rich and organic source of reader feedback, several platform-related limitations should be acknowledged. First, selection bias may be present, as individuals who choose to leave reviews might not represent the broader reading population. Second, positivity bias is a concern, as satisfied readers may be more likely to share their opinions than those who are neutral or dissatisfied. Third, regional and demographic skew could influence the results, especially considering that most reviews in this study originated from Western countries such as Australia, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, and the United States. These factors may limit the generalizability of the findings and should be considered when interpreting the results.

To address these limitations, future studies could incorporate data from multiple platforms—such as Goodreads, LibraryThing, StoryGraph, social media, or book blogs—to diversify sources and reduce platform-specific biases. Cross-platform analyses could reveal important differences in engagement patterns, as each community may vary in user demographics, reviewing norms, and interaction styles. Additionally, collecting demographic metadata where available, or conducting supplementary surveys or interviews with a more representative reader sample, would further enhance the validity and applicability of the findings.

By broadening methodological approaches and data sources, future research can offer a more nuanced and comprehensive understanding of the factors that foster emotional attachment to fiction, and how these dynamics vary across contexts, cultures, and time.

This study demonstrates the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) as an innovative and effective method for exploring and assessing the value of a book using data from online platforms like Amazon. The framework is not only flexible but also cost-effective, as it utilizes R, an open-source software, for all analyses. This makes BMF a practical and accessible tool for replicating and quantitatively analyzing other books and genres. Additionally, the study provides reusable scripts, enabling researchers to adopt and apply this approach easily in future studies.

Disclosure statement

The authors are not aware of any conflict of interest.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: This type of study was exempted from ethical approval.

Ethics Approval: The ethics approval was not required as there were no human participants.

Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was not required as there were no human participants.

Data Availability Statement: For transparency and cost-effectiveness, all the code and data used for this study's analysis have been deposited in Zenodo for public evaluation: [Anonymized]

Acknowledgments: Not applicable

References

- Abrar, M. (2016). Learning From Fables: Moral Values in Three Selected English Stories. *Dinamika Ilmu*, 47-58. <https://doi.org/10.21093/di.v16i1.250>
- Ahmed, S. (2004). *The cultural politics of emotion*. Routledge.
- Ahmed, S., Sharif, T., Ting, D. H., & Sharif, S. J. (2024). Crafting emotional engagement and immersive experiences: Comprehensive scale development for and validation of hospitality marketing storytelling involvement. *Psychology & Marketing*, 41(7), 1514-1529.
- Akhter, T. (2020). Literature and Society: A Critical Analysis of Literary Text through Contemporary Theory. *Talent Development & Excellence*, 12(3), 2228-2234.
- Altun, M. (2023). Literature and Identity: Examine the Role of Literature in Shaping Individual and Cultural Identities. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 10(3).
- Bae, H.-S., Lee, D., & Bae, R. E. (2014). Emotional engagement with the plot and characters: A narrative film on hearing-impaired sexual assault victims. *Narrative Inquiry*, 24(2), 309-327.
- Bal, P. M., & Veltkamp, M. (2013). How Does Fiction Reading Influence Empathy? An Experimental Investigation on the Role of Emotional Transportation. *PLoS ONE*, 8(1), e55341. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0055341>
- Best, J. (2021). To Teach and Delight: The Varieties of Learning From Fiction. *Review of General Psychology*, 25(1), 27-43. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1089268020977173>
- Bouizegarene, N., Ramstead, M. J., Constant, A., Friston, K. J., & Kirmayer, L. J. (2024). Narrative as active inference: an integrative account of cognitive and social functions in adaptation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, 1345480.
- Brecht, B., Hewitt, B., & Bentley, E. (1961). On Chinese acting. *Tulane Drama Review*, 6(1), 130-136. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1125011>
- Brodsky, S. (2024). *The AI-generated books trend is getting worse*. <https://aibusiness.com/responsible-ai/the-ai-generated-books-phenomenon-is-getting-worse>
- Brooks, S. P., & Gelman, A. (1998). General methods for monitoring convergence of iterative simulations. *Journal of computational and graphical statistics*, 7(4), 434-455.
- Brown, S. (2011). And then we come to the brand: academic insights from international bestsellers. *Arts Marketing: An International Journal*, 1(1), 70-86.
- Campbell, J. W. (2019). *The order and the other: Young adult dystopian literature and science fiction*. Univ. Press of Mississippi.
- Chauvin, I., Pierce, L. A., & McDaniel, J. R. (2019). Narrative Reframing of Stories and Fables: Implications for Counseling. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 9(6). <https://doi.org/10.30845/ijhss.v9n6p2>
- Chayka, K. (2025). *A.I. is homogenizing our thoughts*. <https://www.newyorker.com/culture/infinite-scroll/ai-is-homogenizing-our-thoughts>

- Cho, H., Adkins, D., Bossaller, J., & Moulaison-Sandy, H. (2021). Moods in Book Reviews: Text Mining Approach. *Proceedings of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 58(1), 415-419. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/pra2.470>
- Crawford, P. A., Roberts, S. K., & Lacina, J. (2024). Picturebooks and Young Children: Potential, Power, and Practices. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 52(7), 1273-1279. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-024-01701-0>
- Csilléry, K., Blum, M. G., Gaggiotti, O. E., & François, O. (2010). Approximate Bayesian computation (ABC) in practice. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, 25(7), 410-418. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2010.04.001>
- Çubukçu, F. (2011). The Interface Between Critical Thinking Strategies and Moral Development. *Mediterranean Journal of Humanities*, 2(1), 73-85. <https://doi.org/10.13114/mjh/20111790>
- Curcic, D. (2023). *Fiction Books Sales Statistics*. Wordsrated. <https://wordsrated.com/fiction-books-sales/>
- Cuthbertson, A. (2023). *Hundreds of AI-written books flood Amazon*. <https://www.independent.co.uk/tech/ai-author-books-amazon-chatgpt-b2287111.html>
- De Boer, A., van Buel, E. M., & Ter Horst, G. (2012). Love is more than just a kiss: a neurobiological perspective on love and affection. *Neuroscience*, 201, 114-124.
- Denham, A. (2024). Empathy & Literature. *Emotion Review*, 16(2), 84-95.
- Diaconis, P., & Ylvisaker, D. (1985). Quantifying prior opinion. In J. M. Bernardo, M. H. DeGroot, D. V. Lindley, & A. F. M. Smith (Eds.), *Bayesian statistics* (Vol. 2, pp. 133-156). North Holland Press.
- Dunson, D. B. (2001). Commentary: practical advantages of Bayesian analysis of epidemiologic data. *American journal of Epidemiology*, 153(12), 1222-1226. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/153.12.1222>
- Fehr, B., & Russell, J. A. (1991). The concept of love viewed from a prototype perspective. *Journal of Personality Social Psychology*, 60(3), 425. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.60.3.425>
- Fish, S. (1995). Is there a text in this class? In J. Arthur (Ed.), *Campus wars* (pp. 49-56). Routledge.
- Fong, K., Mullin, J. B., & Mar, R. A. (2013). What You Read Matters: The Role of Fiction Genre in Predicting Interpersonal Sensitivity. *Psychology of Aesthetics Creativity and the Arts*, 7(4), 370-376. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0034084>
- Garces-Bacsal, R. M. (2022). Diverse books for diverse children: Building an early childhood diverse booklist for social and emotional learning. *Journal of Early Childhood Literacy*, 22(1), 66-95.
- Gill, J. (2014). *Bayesian methods: A social and behavioral sciences approach* (Vol. 20). CRC press.
- Gwekwerere, T. (2018). Universal, normative, and indispensable: exploring the emphasis on eurocentric literary-critical perspectives in the criticism of the black zimbabwean novel. *Journal of Black Studies*, 49(8), 801-819.
- Halsey, L. G., Curran-Everett, D., Vowler, S. L., & Drummond, G. B. (2015). The fickle P value generates irreproducible results. *Nature methods*, 12, 179-185. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.3288>
- Hartung, F., Wang, Y., Mak, M., Willems, R., & Chatterjee, A. (2021). Aesthetic appraisals of literary style and emotional intensity in narrative engagement are neurally dissociable. *Communications biology*, 4(1), 1401.
- Hertog, T. (2023). *On the origin of time: Stephen Hawking's final theory*. Random House. https://www.google.com/books/edition/On_the_Origin_of_Time/1IBTEAAAQBAJ

- Ho, M.-T., & Ho, M.-T. (2025). Three tragedies that shape human life in age of AI and their antidotes. *AI & SOCIETY*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-025-02316-8>
- Ho, M.-T., & Vuong, Q.-H. (2025). Five premises to understand human-computer interactions as AI is changing the world. *AI & SOCIETY*, 40, 1161–1162. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-024-01913-3>
- Horton Jr, C. B., White, M. W., & Iyengar, S. S. (2023). Bias against AI art can enhance perceptions of human creativity. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 19001. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-45202-3>
- Iser, W. (1972). The reading process: A phenomenological approach. *New Literary History*, 3(2), 279-299. <https://doi.org/10.2307/468316>
- Ivey, G. (2014). The Social Side of Engaged Reading for Young Adolescents. *The Reading Teacher*, 68(3), 165-171. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/trtr.1268>
- Johnson, M. J., & Simpson, H. A. (2022). *Social Media Marketing for Book Publishers*. Routledge.
- Jones, C. W., & Paris, C. (2018). It's the end of the world and they know it: How dystopian fiction shapes political attitudes. *Perspectives on Politics*, 16(4), 969-989.
- Keen, S. (2006). A theory of narrative empathy. *Narrative*, 14(3), 207-236.
- Kent, M. L. (2015). The power of storytelling in public relations: Introducing the 20 master plots. *Public Relations Review*, 41(4), 480-489.
- Kgopa, M., & Mathe, D. (2022). Sociocultural Themes in Selected Northern Sotho Fables: The Motif-Index Perspective. *Southern African Journal for Folklore Studies*, 31(1), 20 pages. <https://doi.org/10.25159/2663-6697/7915>
- Koliada, E., & Kalynovska, I. (2023). Representation of sensory perceptions and emotional responses in the language of literary texts. *RESEARCH TRENDS IN MODERN LINGUISTICS AND LITERATURE*, 6, 27-39.
- Konrad, M. H. (2023). The Love of the Book: Students' Text Selection and Their Motivation to Read. *The Reading Teacher*, 77(3), 332-340. <https://doi.org/10.1002/trtr.2246>
- Koopman, E. M., & Hakemulder, F. (2015). Effects of Literature on Empathy and Self-Reflection: A Theoretical-Empirical Framework. *Journal of Literary Theory*, 9(1), 79-111. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1515/jlt-2015-0005>
- La, V.-P., & Vuong, Q.-H. (2019). bayesvl: Visually learning the graphical structure of Bayesian networks and performing MCMC with 'Stan'. *The Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN)*. <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/bayesvl/index.html>
- Layous, K., Kurtz, J. L., Wildschut, T., & Sedikides, C. (2022). The effect of a multi-week nostalgia intervention on well-being: Mechanisms and moderation. *Emotion*, 22(8), 1952-1968. <https://doi.org/10.1037/emo0000817>
- Lisnani, L. (2019). The Effect of Fable on Increasing Students' Understanding of Plane Figure Concept. International Conference on Educational Sciences and Teacher Profession (ICETeP 2018),
- Luțan, E.-R., & Bădică, C. (2022). Emotion-Based Literature Book Classification Using Online Reviews. *Electronics*, 11(20), 3412. <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/11/20/3412>
- Manggong, L. (2019). Subaltern Voice and Marginal Moral Lessons in Suniti Namjoshi's Feminist Fables. *Fabula*, 60(1-2), 132-144. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1515/fabula-2019-0009>
- Mar, R. A., Oatley, K., & Peterson, J. B. (2009). Exploring the link between reading fiction and empathy: Ruling out individual differences and examining outcomes. *Communications*, 34(4), 407-428. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1515/COMM.2009.025>

- Mart, C. (2019). Reader-response theory and literature discussions: A Springboard for exploring literary texts. *The New Educational Review*, 56(2), 78-87. <https://doi.org/10.15804/ner.2019.56.2.06>
- Massumi, B. (1995). The autonomy of affect. *Cultural Critique*, 31, 83-109. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1354446>
- McElreath, R. (2018). *Statistical rethinking: A Bayesian course with examples in R and Stan*. Chapman and Hall/CRC.
- Mendrofa, M. P. (2020). Reading fiction for better life in Luis Sepulveda's The old man who read love stories. *Elite English and Literature Journal*, 7(2), 125. <https://doi.org/10.24252/10.24252/elite.v7i2a2>
- Merga, M. K., McRae, M., & Rutherford, L. (2017). Adolescents' attitudes toward talking about books: Implications for educators. *English in Education*, n/a(n/a). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/eie.12144>
- Merga, M. K., & Roni, S. M. (2018). Characteristics, Preferences and Motivation of Avid Non-Fiction Readers. *Collection and Curation*, 37(2), 50-59. <https://doi.org/10.1108/cc-05-2017-0019>
- Nesin, A. (2002). *Laugh Or Lament?: Selected Short Stories of Aziz Nesin* (Vol. 426). Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Turkey.
- Nguyen, M.-H. (2024). How can satirical fables offer us a vision for sustainability? *Visions for Sustainability*, 23(11267), 323-328. <https://doi.org/10.13135/2384-8677/11267>
- Nguyen, M.-H., La, V.-P., Le, T.-T., & Vuong, Q.-H. (2022). Introduction to Bayesian Mindsponge Framework analytics: An innovative method for social and psychological research. *MethodsX*, 9, 101808. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mex.2022.101808>
- Nussbaum, M. C. (2001). *Upheavals of thought: The intelligence of emotions*. Cambridge University Press.
- Oloff, M., Frijling, J. L., Kubzansky, L. D., Bradley, B., Ellenbogen, M. A., Cardoso, C., . . . Van Zuiden, M. (2013). The role of oxytocin in social bonding, stress regulation and mental health: an update on the moderating effects of context and interindividual differences. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 38(9), 1883-1894.
- Orwell, G. (2021). *Animal farm*. Oxford University Press.
- Paredes, L. P., & Aliagas, C. (2022). Literacy and Literary Learning on <scp>BookTube</Scp> Through the Lenses of Latina <scp>BookTubers</Scp>. *Literacy*, 57(1), 17-27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lit.12310>
- Park, S. (2022). The Fable and the Novel: Rethinking History of Korean Fiction from the Perspective of Narrative Aesthetics. *The Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism*, 80(3), 374-379. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jaac/kpac031>
- Parsons, L. T. (2013). An examination of fourth graders' aesthetic engagement with literary characters. *Reading Psychology*, 34(1), 1-25.
- Pelletier, J., & Beatty, R. (2015). Children's understanding of Aesop's fables: relations to reading comprehension and theory of mind. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.01448>
- Read, W., Robertson, N., & McQuilken, L. (2011). A Novel Romance: The Technology Acceptance Model With Emotional Attachment. *Australasian Marketing Journal (Amj)*, 19(4), 223-229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ausmj.2011.07.004>

- Reagan, A. J., Mitchell, L., Kiley, D., Danforth, C. M., & Dodds, P. S. (2016). The emotional arcs of stories are dominated by six basic shapes. *EPJ Data Science*, 5(1), 31. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjds/s13688-016-0093-1>
- Reis, H. T., & Aron, A. (2008). Love: What is it, why does it matter, and how does it operate? *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 3(1), 80-86. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6916.2008.00065.x>
- Rosenblatt, L. M. (1978). *The reader, the text, the poem: The transactional theory of the literary work*. Southern Illinois University Press.
- Rothbauer, P., & Harrington, M. R. (2022). Honouring a Love of Books and Reading in Library and Information Science. *Proceedings of the Annual Conference of Cais / Actes Du Congrès Annuel De L Acsi*. <https://doi.org/10.29173/cais1252>
- Rovelli, C. (2018). *Reality is not what it seems: The journey to quantum gravity*. Penguin. https://www.google.com/books/edition/Reality_Is_Not_What_It_Seems/fsQiDAAAQBAJ
- Salih, R. S. (2024). The Relationship between Literature and the Senses. *International Journal of English Language, Education and Literature Studies*, 3(3), 70-76.
- Sedikides, C., Wildschut, T., Routledge, C., Arndt, J., Hepper, E. G., & Zhou, X. (2015). To nostalgize: Mixing memory with affect and desire. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, 51, 189-273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.aesp.2014.10.001>
- Serenko, A., Bontis, N., & Moshonsky, M. (2012). Books as a Knowledge Translation Mechanism: Citation Analysis and Author Survey. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 16(3), 495-511. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673271211238797>
- Shannon, C. E. (1948). A mathematical theory of communication. *The Bell System Technical Journal*, 27(3), 379-423. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1538-7305.1948.tb01338.x>
- Smith, G. (2015). Readership, the fables of the elegiac Romulus, and the Morall Fabillis of Robert Henryson [Article]. *Philological Quarterly*, 94, 51+. <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A436542100/LitRC?u=anon~d0bda6f8&sid=googleScholar&xid=e7138276>
- Soni, S. (2024). Anthropomorphism as an art of storytelling: Exploring Aesthetics and Ethical Implications in Children's Literature. *International Journal For Multidisciplinary Research*.
- Southerton, D., Olsen, W., Warde, A., & Cheng, S.-L. (2012). Practices and trajectories: A comparative analysis of reading in France, Norway, the Netherlands, the UK and the USA. *Journal of Consumer Culture*, 12(3), 237-262. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469540512456920>
- Spence, C. (2020). The Multisensory Experience of Handling and Reading Books. *Multisensory Research*, 33(8), 902-928. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22134808-bja10015>
- Stansfield, J., & Bunce, L. (2014). The Relationship Between Empathy and Reading Fiction: Separate Roles for Cognitive and Affective Components. *Journal of European Psychology Students*, 5(3), 9-18. <https://doi.org/10.5334/jeps.ca>
- Theresia, N., & Recard, M. (2021). Applying multisensory approach to promote engagement in primary English home-based learning. *ELTR Journal*, 5(2), 105-119.
- Thumala Olave, M. A. (2018). Reading matters: Towards a cultural sociology of reading. *American Journal of Cultural Sociology*, 6(3), 417-454. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41290-017-0034-x>
- Thumala Olave, M. A. (2020). Book love. A cultural sociological interpretation of the attachment to books. *Poetics*, 81, 101440. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.poetic.2020.101440>

- Thumala Olave, M. A. (2022). Reading matters: Toward a cultural sociology of reading. In M. A. Thumala Olave (Ed.), *The Cultural Sociology of Reading: The Meanings of Reading and Books Across the World* (pp. 19-61). Springer.
- Tran, T. T. (2025). Flying beyond didacticism: The creative environmental vision of ‘Wild Wise Weird’. <https://youngvoicesofscience.org/?p=1963>
- Tzu, C. (2006). *The Book of Chuang Tzu*. Penguin UK.
- Vehtari, A., & Gabry, J. (2019). *Bayesian Stacking and Pseudo-BMA weights using the loo package*. In (Version loo 2.2.0) <https://mc-stan.org/loo/articles/loo2-weights.html>
- Vehtari, A., Gelman, A., & Gabry, J. (2017). Practical Bayesian model evaluation using leave-one-out cross-validation and WAIC. *Statistics and computing*, 27(5), 1413-1432. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11222-016-9696-4>
- Vuong, Q.-H. (2023). *Mindsponge theory*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://books.google.com/books?id=OSiGEAAAQBAJ>
- Vuong, Q.-H. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. AISDL. <https://books.google.com/books?&id=rq82EQAAQBAJ>
- Vuong, Q.-H., & Nguyen, M.-H. (2024a). *Better economics for the Earth: A lesson from quantum and information theories*. AISDL. <https://books.google.com/books?id=I50TEQAAQBAJ>
- Vuong, Q.-H., & Nguyen, M.-H. (2024b). Exploring the role of rejection in scholarly knowledge production: Insights from granular interaction thinking and information theory. *Learned Publishing*, e1636. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1636>
- Vuong, Q.-H., & Nguyen, M.-H. (2025). On Nature Quotient. <https://philarchive.org/rec/VUOONQ>
- Vuong, Q.-H., Nguyen, M.-H., & La, V.-P. (2022). *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://books.google.com/books?id=EGeEEAAAQBAJ>
- Wagenmakers, E.-J., Marsman, M., Jamil, T., Ly, A., Verhagen, J., Love, J., . . . Epskamp, S. (2018). Bayesian inference for psychology. Part I: Theoretical advantages and practical ramifications. *Psychonomic bulletin review*, 25(1), 35-57. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-017-1343-3>
- Waheed, M., Kaur, K., Ain, N.-u., & Sanni, S. A. (2015). Emotional Attachment and Multidimensional Self-Efficacy: Extension of Innovation Diffusion Theory in the Context of eBook Reader. *Behaviour and Information Technology*, 34(12), 1147-1159. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144929x.2015.1004648>
- Watson, A. (2024). *Print book unit sales in the U.S. 2013-2023, by category (in 1,000s)*. Weekly. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/422648/print-book-sales-usa-by-category/>
- Wielded. (2024). *The future of niche writing: Surviving (and thriving) in an AI-powered world*. <https://wielded.com/blog/the-future-of-niche-writing-surviving-and-thriving-in-an-ai-powered-world>
- Winkler, J. R., Appel, M., Schmidt, M.-L. C., & Richter, T. (2023). The experience of emotional shifts in narrative persuasion. *Media Psychology*, 26(2), 141-171.
- Zhang, J., & Liu, Y. (2022). Exploration of Emotion Perception in Serious Interactive Digital Narrative. *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 2022(1), 8160695. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/8160695>